

Mental Health Services Utilization in Patients with Major Depressive Disorder and Personality Disorders: A Retrospective Analysis in a Mexican Tertiary-Level Psychiatric Hospital

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Resumen

■ INTRODUCCIÓN

El trastorno depresivo mayor (TDM) y los trastornos de personalidad (TP) son comorbilidades frecuentes que agravan la atención clínica. Las personas con ambas condiciones suelen requerir hospitalizaciones más prolongadas y regímenes terapéuticos complejos, lo que incrementa significativamente la utilización de los servicios de salud mental.

Objetivo: Evaluar la asociación entre la presencia de TP y la utilización de servicios de salud mental en individuos hospitalizados con TDM en un hospital psiquiátrico de tercer nivel en México.

Materiales y Métodos: Estudio retrospectivo basado en diagnósticos de TDM según los criterios del Manual Diagnóstico y Estadístico de los Trastornos Mentales, Cuarta Edición (DSM-IV, por sus siglas en inglés). Se analizaron variables sociodemográficas, clínicas y de utilización de servicios mediante análisis estadístico descriptivo y modelos multivariados.

Resultados: Se incluyó a 237 participantes. Los individuos con TDM y TP presentaron un mayor número de hospitalizaciones, tratamientos farmacológicos más complejos y una edad promedio menor en el primer ingreso hospitalario en comparación con aquellos sin TP.

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Conclusiones: La comorbilidad con TP incrementa la complejidad clínica y los recursos necesarios para la atención de pacientes con TDM en un hospital de tercer nivel.

Palabras Clave: *Trastorno depresivo mayor; Trastornos de Personalidad; Servicios de Salud Mental; Hospitalización.*

ABSTRACT

Background: Major depressive Disorder (MDD) and personality disorders (PD) are frequent comorbidities that exacerbate clinical complexity. Individuals with both conditions often require prolonged hospitalizations and intricate therapeutic regimens, significantly increasing the utilization of mental health services. This study underscores the urgent need for integrated care models, which involve coordinated and collaborative care among different healthcare providers, to address the complex needs of these patients.

Objective: To evaluate the association between the presence of PD and the utilization of mental health services among individuals hospitalized with MDD in a Mexican tertiary-level psychiatric hospital.

Materials and Methods: A retrospective study was conducted on MDD diagnosis according to the *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders*, Fourth Edition (DSM-IV). Socio-demographic, clinical, and service utilization variables were analyzed using descriptive statistics and multivariate models.

Results: A total of 237 participants were included. Individuals with MDD and PD exhibited a higher number of hospitalizations, more complex pharmacological treatments, and a younger average age at their first hospitalization compared to those without PD.

Conclusions: PD comorbidity increases clinical complexity and healthcare resource utilization among MDD patients in tertiary-level psychiatric care.

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Keywords: *Major Depressive Disorder; Personality Disorders; Mental Health Services; Hospitalization.*

■ BACKGROUND

Major Depressive Disorder (MDD)

MDD is a global health challenge due to its high prevalence, chronicity, association with disability, and reduced quality of life. It imposes significant economic and societal burdens, escalating health-care costs worldwide (Greenberg et al., 2015). Epidemiological data suggest that the prevalence of MDD is rising, particularly among younger populations. Furthermore, notable sex disparities exist, with females exhibiting higher diagnostic rates (5.5%) compared to males (3.2%) (Ferrari et al., 2013; Ishikawa et al., 2015; Maske et al., 2016). MDD episodes last approximately 37.7 weeks on average, disproportionately affecting individuals during their most productive years and amplifying personal, familial, and societal burdens (Greenberg et al., 2015).

The etiology of MDD results from a complex interplay of biological, psychological, and environmental factors. For instance, early-life adversities, such as parental psychiatric disorders or chronic exposure to significant stressors, significantly heighten the risk of developing MDD (Li et al., 2015). Additionally, personality traits like high harm avoidance and low self-directedness are frequently observed in individuals with MDD, distinguishing them from other mood disorders like Bipolar I and II (Zaninotto et al., 2016).

Personality Disorders (PD)

According to the *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition* (DSM-5)

(American Psychiatric Association [APA], 2013), PD is characterized by enduring, inflexible, and maladaptive patterns of cognition, emotion, and behavior that impair functioning in various domains. These disorders often complicate treatment plans due to emotional dysregulation, interpersonal conflicts, and resistance to standard interventions for mood disorders (APA, 2013). Empirical data support these challenges: Bender et al. (2001) found that individuals with PD were 1.79 times more likely to require hospitalization and engaged in psychotherapy services at rates five times higher than those without PD. Hörz et al. (2010) further emphasized the chronic, recurrent nature of borderline personality disorder (BPD), characterized by frequent treatment discontinuation and subsequent re-engagement.

Comorbidity Between MDD and PD

The co-occurrence of MDD and PD creates a clinically distinct and multifaceted presentation. This comorbidity, which refers to the simultaneous presence of two or more chronic conditions in a patient, increases symptom severity, recurrence rates, and functional impairments, thereby complicating treatment approaches. Moreover, individuals with both MDD and PD are at heightened risk for suicidal ideation, self-injurious behaviors, and impulsivity (Nigatu et al., 2015; Alegria et al., 2013). Shared risk factors, including prolonged exposure to chronic stress and adverse life events, further compound these challenges (Zaninotto et al., 2016).

Statistical analyses reveal significant associations between PD and adverse clinical outcomes in MDD populations. For example, patients with comorbid PD exhibit earlier onset of symptoms, higher treatment resistance, and increased psychiatric

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comorbidities, necessitating multidisciplinary care strategies (Sansone et al., 1998; Davidson, 2002).

Impact on Mental Health Service Utilization

The intersection of MDD and PD substantially influences mental health service utilization, particularly in specialized care settings. Individuals with these comorbidities require prolonged, intensive, multidisciplinary interventions to address their complex clinical needs. Davidson (2002) reported nearly double the healthcare utilization rates among individuals with PD compared to those without such diagnoses.

Similarly, historical evidence corroborates this trend. Reich et al. (1989) found elevated rates of hospitalization and outpatient consultations among patients with PD compared to the general population. Sansone et al. (1998) highlighted that women with BPD were exceptionally high utilizers of healthcare services, underscoring the strain these comorbidities place on psychiatric care systems.

■ JUSTIFICATION

Despite the high prevalence and significant clinical implications of MDD and PD comorbidities, research exploring their combined impact on healthcare utilization remains limited, particularly in developing nations. Most existing studies focus on outpatient populations, often neglecting hospitalized individuals' unique utilization patterns and challenges. This study aims to fill this gap by investigating the utilization patterns of mental health services among inpatients diagnosed with MDD, with and without PD comorbidities, in a tertiary-level psychiatric hospital in Mexico. Through this research, we aim to provide

actionable insights that can guide resource allocation and inform the development of integrated care models tailored to the needs of this high-risk population.

This study addresses these gaps by investigating the utilization patterns of mental health services among inpatients diagnosed with MDD, with and without PD comorbidities, in a tertiary-level psychiatric hospital in Mexico. Through this research, we aim to provide actionable insights that can guide resource allocation and inform the development of integrated care models tailored to the needs of this high-risk population.

■ OBJECTIVES

To document and assess the association between the presence of PD and the utilization of mental health services in individuals hospitalized with MDD.

■ MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design and Setting

This research employed a retrospective, descriptive, comparative, and correlational design. It was conducted at the *Instituto Nacional de Psiquiatría Ramón de la Fuente Muñiz* (INPRFM) in Mexico City. Data collection included comprehensive reviews of clinical records and institutional databases for patients hospitalized between January 1 and December 31, 2000.

Sample

The study included participants aged 18 years or older who were hospitalized during the specified period with a primary diagnosis of MDD accord-

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ing to DSM-IV criteria (APA, 2000). Inclusion criteria required participants to have completed inpatient care during the study period and have documented outpatient follow-up. Participants were excluded if they were diagnosed with bipolar disorder, schizophrenia, schizoaffective disorder, or any psychotic disorder or if they discontinued outpatient follow-up after hospitalization. Sampling was open and convenience-based.

Variables

The primary independent variable was the presence of PD, categorized into three levels: no diagnosis, subthreshold traits, and a complete PD diagnosis by DSM-IV criteria (APA, 2000). The dependent variables included sociodemographic characteristics (sex, educational attainment, and employment status), clinical outcomes (age at first hospitalization, comorbid Axis I disorders, history of suicide attempts, and lifetime substance use), and service utilization measures (duration of institutional care, number of hospitalizations, number of medications prescribed, and attendance at outpatient services).

Data Collection

Data were extracted from hospital databases and clinical records. Diagnoses were confirmed using DSM-IV criteria (APA, 2000). Two independent reviewers resolved any discrepancies through *Delphi* consensus.

Statistical Analysis

The analysis was conducted in two stages. In the first stage, a comparative analysis was performed to identify differences between groups based on the presence of Personality Disorder (PD). Quan-

titative variables were analyzed using one-way ANOVA with post hoc Scheffé tests, categorical variables were assessed using chi-square tests (X^2), and ordinal variables were examined using the Mantel-Haenszel linear association procedure. All analyses in this stage were conducted using SPSS version 25.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY).

In the second stage, correlational analysis was performed using path analysis and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). Variables with high bivariate correlations were carefully selected to minimize collinearity, and stepwise multiple regression models were constructed using backward elimination criteria ($p < 0.001$ for inclusion, $p > 0.002$ for exclusion). SEM was conducted using AMOS version 6.3 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY), with model fit evaluated through the chi-square/degrees of freedom ratio (X^2/df ; acceptable range: 2–3), Adjusted Goodness-of-Fit Index (AGFI; > 0.80), and Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA; < 0.08 with a 90% confidence interval).

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to ethical principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki and complied with national regulations for research involving human participants. Before initiating the study, approval was obtained from the INPRFM Research Ethics Committee (Approval Folio: 001-11241-M4-2004). As this was a retrospective study with anonymized data, informed consent was not required. All measures were taken to ensure participant confidentiality, including secure storage of data handling and de-identifying personal information.

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■ RESULTS

Initially, 258 participants were recruited; however, 21 were excluded due to a lack of outpatient follow-up, resulting in a final sample of $n = 237$. The sample comprised 144 women (60.8%; 95% CI: 54.5%–66.8%) and 93 men (39.2%; 95% CI: 33.2%–45.5%), with a mean age of 34.7 ± 9.2 years (range: 18–60).

Sociodemographic Characteristics

Educational attainment showed that $n = 53$ participants (22.4%; 95% CI: 17.4%–28.2%) had completed primary education, $n = 140$ (59.1%; 95% CI: 52.7%–65.2%) had middle or high school education, and $n = 44$ (18.5%; 95% CI: 14.0%–24.1%) had university-level education. Employment status revealed that $n = 52$ participants (21.9%; 95% CI: 16.9%–27.8%) were unemployed, $n = 123$ (51.9%; 95% CI: 45.4%–58.3%) were engaged in unpaid domestic or caregiving work, and $n = 62$ (26.2%; 95% CI: 20.8%–32.4%) held paid employment. Complete data is shown in **Table 1**.

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Table 1: Sociodemographic Distribution Among Groups by PD Classification

Studied Variable	Without disorder (n, %)	With Traits (n, %)	With disorder (n, %)	χ^2	p
Sex	-	-	-	3.48	0.175
Female	33 (17.8%)	92 (49.7%)	60 (32.4%)	-	-
Male	12 (23.1%)	30 (57.7%)	10 (19.2%)	-	-
Educational Attainment	-	-	-	17.15	0.002**
Primary	20 (37.7%)	24 (45.3%)	9 (17.0%)	-	-
Middle and High School	20 (14.3%)	75 (53.6%)	45 (32.1%)	-	-
Higher Education	5 (11.4%)	23 (52.3%)	16 (36.4%)	-	-
Employment Status	-	-	-	3.37	0.498
Unemployed	11 (21.2%)	24 (46.2%)	17 (32.7%)	-	-
Unpaid Domestic/Care Work	25 (20.3%)	60 (48.8%)	38 (30.9%)	-	-
Paid Employment	9 (14.5%)	38 (61.3%)	15 (24.2%)	-	-

Note: This table summarizes sociodemographic characteristics across groups classified by personality disorder status: without disorder, with traits, and with disorder. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) were observed in educational attainment, suggesting variations in personality disorder prevalence across educational levels.

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Comorbidities

Comorbid Axis I disorders were present in 37.6% of participants ($n = 89$; 95% CI: 31.9%–43.7%), with 8.9% ($n = 21$; 95% CI: 5.9%–13.2%) having two or more disorders. The most frequent comorbidities were anxiety disorders (20.7%; $n = 49$; 95% CI: 15.8%–26.6%). Other comorbid conditions included obsessive-compulsive disorder (4.2%; $n = 10$; 95% CI: 2.2%–7.6%) and eating disorders (0.8%; $n = 2$; 95% CI: 0.1%–3.1%).

Personality Disorders (PD)

PD was present in 29.5% of participants ($n = 70$; 95% CI: 23.9%–35.9%), with subthreshold PD traits observed in 51.5% ($n = 122$; 95% CI: 45.0%–57.8%) and 19.0% ($n = 45$; 95% CI: 14.2%–24.6%) showing no evidence of PD. Among those diagnosed with PD, Cluster B disorders were the most prevalent ($n = 41$; 58.2%), followed by Cluster C ($n = 23$; 32.1%) and Cluster A ($n = 3$; 4.6%). BPD was the most common PD within Cluster B, accounting for 63.4% ($n = 26$; 95% CI: 50.0%–75.0%) of this group.

Correlations with PD

No significant differences were observed between sexes in the presence of PD ($X^2 = 3.48$, $p = 0.175$). Among women ($n = 144$), 22.9% ($n = 33$; 95% CI: 16.4%–30.8%) had no PD, 63.9% ($n = 92$; 95% CI: 55.7%–71.5%) exhibited subthreshold traits, and 41.7% ($n = 60$; 95% CI: 33.8%–50.1%) were diagnosed with PD. For men ($n = 93$), 12.9% ($n = 12$; 95% CI: 7.5%–21.4%) showed no PD, 66.7% ($n = 30$; 95% CI: 56.2%–75.5%) exhibited subthreshold traits, and 20.4% ($n = 10$; 95% CI: 11.4%–34.1%) were diagnosed with PD. Educational attainment showed significant differences: higher-education

participants were more likely to meet PD criteria ($X^2 = 17.15$, $p = 0.002$). For instance, 37.7% ($n = 20$; 95% CI: 25.5%–51.4%) of those with primary education had no PD, compared to only 11.4% ($n = 5$; 95% CI: 4.7%–24.4%) of those with a university degree.

Health Service Utilization

Participants with PD demonstrated significantly higher use of health services. Those with PD spent an average of 46.93 ± 14.5 months (95% CI: 42.8–51.0, range: 12–84) as institutional clients, compared to 35.87 ± 12.3 months (95% CI: 32.4–39.3, range: 10–65) for those without PD ($F(2,234) = 18.61$, $p < 0.001$). Participants with subthreshold PD traits had an intermediate duration of 40.07 ± 13.8 months (95% CI: 36.7–43.4, range: 15–70).

Similarly, participants with PD had a higher number of hospitalizations, averaging 2.16 ± 1.2 (95% CI: 1.9–2.4, range: 1–5), compared to 1.27 ± 0.9 (95% CI: 1.0–1.5, range: 1–3) for those without PD ($F(2,234) = 10.50$, $p < 0.001$). Subthreshold PD traits were associated with an intermediate average of 1.48 ± 1.0 hospitalizations (95% CI: 1.2–1.7, range: 1–4).

Pharmacological intervention patterns also differed significantly. Participants with PD were prescribed an average of 4.36 ± 1.5 medications (95% CI: 3.9–4.7, range: 2–7), compared to 2.84 ± 1.2 (95% CI: 2.5–3.2, range: 1–5) for those without PD ($F(2,234) = 13.65$, $p < 0.001$). Those with subthreshold traits had a mean of 3.67 ± 1.4 medications (95% CI: 3.3–4.0, range: 2–6), closely aligning with the PD group. The rest of the data is illustrated in **Table 2** and **Table 3**.

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Table 2: Health Service Utilization by PD Status,

Group	Mean Duration as Client (months)	Hospitalizations (mean)	Medications Prescribed (mean)
With PD	46.93 ± 14.5	2.16 ± 1.2	4.36 ± 1.5
Without PD	35.87 ± 12.3	1.27 ± 0.9	2.84 ± 1.2
Subthreshold Traits	40.07 ± 13.8	1.48 ± 1.0	3.67 ± 1.4

Note: Data include participants diagnosed with Personality Disorders (PD), those without PD, and those exhibiting subthreshold traits. The table highlights significant differences in health service utilization, including duration as institutional clients, frequency of hospitalizations, and the number of medications prescribed

Table 3: Comparison of Variables Between Groups With and Without PD.

Studied Variable	Without Disorder (Mean ± SD)	With Disorder (Mean ± SD)	Significance (F(df), p)
Time as a patient in the hospital (months)	35.87 ± 19.75	46.93 ± 28.71	(1,113) = 5.114, p = 0.026
Periods in treatment	1.38 ± 0.68	1.63 ± 1.08	(1,113) = 1.929, p = 0.168
Number of hospital admissions	1.27 ± 0.62	2.16 ± 1.37	F(1,113) = 16.802, p < 0.001
Number of hospital days	1.27 ± 0.62	2.16 ± 1.37	F(1,113) = 16.802, p < 0.001
Age at first hospital admission (years)	34.02 ± 24.18	54.16 ± 46.69	F(1,113) = 7.125, p = 0.009
Attendance to external consultation	16.11 ± 15.51	15.51 ± 13.91	F(1,113) = 0.046, p = 0.83

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Absences of external consultation	3.33 ± 2.88	5.40 ± 5.18	F(1,113) = 5.969, p = 0.016
Attendance to psychotherapy sessions	4.04 ± 8.96	5.17 ± 9.79	F(1,113) = 0.387, p = 0.535
Absences of psychotherapy sessions	0.89 ± 1.82	1.73 ± 2.95	F(1,113) = 2.924, p = 0.09
Emergency consultations	1.02 ± 1.27	1.74 ± 2.28	F(1,113) = 3.753, p = 0.055
Internal medicine appointments	1.07 ± 3.14	0.46 ± 1.46	F(1,113) = 1.975, p = 0.163
Neurology appointments	0.27 ± 0.58	0.27 ± 1.24	F(1,113) = 0.001, p = 0.981
Laboratory tests	4.47 ± 3.62	4.59 ± 3.43	F(1,113) = 0.032, p = 0.859
Brain imaging studies	1.18 ± 0.65	1.21 ± 0.54	F(1,113) = 0.108, p = 0.744
Electroencephalography studies	2.07 ± 1.01	2.10 ± 1.36	F(1,113) = 0.02, p = 0.888
Number of prescribed medications	2.84 ± 1.24	4.36 ± 1.97	(1,113) = 21.08, p < 0.001
Use of drugs of abuse	0.44 ± 0.69	1.23 ± 1.26	(1,113) = 14.477, p < 0.001

Note: This table summarizes the distribution of studied variables between groups with and without a diagnosed personality disorder. Significant differences (p < 0.05) are observed in several domains, including hospital admissions, number of prescribed medications, and use of drugs of abuse.

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Discussion

The findings of this study emphasize the significant influence of PD comorbidity on healthcare utilization and clinical outcomes among individuals with MDD. Patients with PD required longer durations of care, were hospitalized at younger ages, and exhibited more complex pharmacological needs compared to those without PD. These results align with previous research indicating that PD amplifies the severity of depressive episodes, complicates treatment pathways, and places substantial demands on healthcare systems (Bender et al., 2001; Davidson, 2002).

Sociodemographic Variations

The sociodemographic analysis revealed critical insights into the distribution of PD within the sample. Women accounted for most participants, a finding consistent with the established higher prevalence of MDD among females (Ferrari et al., 2013). Higher educational attainment was paradoxically associated with a greater likelihood of PD diagnosis, potentially reflecting improved access to diagnostic services or increased awareness among educated individuals (Hueston et al., 1996). Furthermore, employment status played a significant role, with high unemployment rates observed among participants with PD. This suggests a cyclical relationship wherein occupational instability exacerbates interpersonal dysfunction, while PD traits impair job retention and socioeconomic stability (Magallón-Neri et al., 2012).

Comorbidities and Clinical Complexity

The study highlighted a high prevalence of Axis I comorbidities, particularly anxiety disorders, among participants with PD. Such comorbid

conditions exacerbate clinical complexity, often requiring integrated therapeutic approaches to address both primary and secondary psychopathologies effectively. These findings signal the need for comprehensive, personalized treatment strategies tailored to this population's unique challenges (Trull et al., 2010).

Healthcare Utilization Patterns

Patients with PD demonstrated significantly greater healthcare utilization, characterized by extended care durations and higher hospitalization rates. Notably, these individuals were hospitalized at younger ages, highlighting the need for early detection and intervention to mitigate the long-term burden of PD traits, particularly during adolescence or early adulthood (Livesley et al., 1993). Additionally, the observed increase in the number of prescribed medications reflects the complex interplay between PD and MDD, necessitating meticulous pharmacological management combined with psychosocial interventions.

Strengths

This study provides valuable data on the interplay between MDD and PD in a hospitalized population, one of the most clinically severe and resource-intensive settings.

Limitations

Despite its contributions, the study has notable limitations. The retrospective design, reliant on clinical records, may introduce bias due to incomplete or inconsistent documentation. While appropriate for the study period, the application of DSM-IV criteria limits comparability with research utilizing newer diagnostic frameworks.

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Additionally, unmeasured variables, including cultural influences, healthcare disparities, and social stigma, may have mediated the outcomes and warrant further exploration.

Future Directions

Future research should adopt DSM-5 traditional or newer dimensional criteria to investigate dimensional PD traits and their clinical implications comprehensively. Efforts should focus on developing and evaluating integrative care models that combine pharmacological and psychosocial interventions tailored to the needs of individuals with comorbid MDD and PD. Moreover, exploring the impact of healthcare access disparities in resource-limited settings could inform policies to achieve equitable mental healthcare delivery.

CONCLUSIONS

This study shows the impact of PD comorbidity on the healthcare trajectories of individuals with MDD. Patients with PD experience higher hospitalization rates, longer care durations, and more intricate pharmacological regimens, reflecting the chronic and resource-intensive nature of these conditions. Sociodemographic factors, such as sex, education, and employment, further influence service utilization patterns, underscoring the importance of personalized, multidimensional care strategies. These findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the challenges posed by comorbid MDD and PD and highlight the need for proactive, integrative care approaches tailored to this population's complex needs.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors lack conflicts of interest to disclose.

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